

Sensitivity method for structural model update and identification in finite elements using vibration measurements

LF Barazzutti¹, HM Gomes¹, LRC Drehmer²

¹Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, RS, 90050-170, Brazil.

²Federal University of Santa Maria, Cachoeira do Sul, RS, 96506-302, Brazil.

ABSTRACT: Geometric simplifications, choice of boundary conditions (loads and supports), modeling of connections and interfaces between components, as well as standardized material property values definition are steps that compose the process of idealization of a finite element model. Therefore, it is evident that, during these steps, numerous unknown and uncertain variables can cause discrepancies between the results of the numerical model and the experimental model. This justifies the importance of model identification as a structural optimization problem, that is, the use of computational processes that allow calibrating the numerical model so that the error between numerical and experimental results is minimized [1]. There are several methodologies to perform model identification, however, one that has been extensively studied is the sensitivity method that allows updating the finite element model so that it reproduces not only the average result of the experimental tests but also allows updating their covariance, that is, to adjust the numerical model to statistically reproduce the experimental model. This same approach was used in [2]. For this application, a prototype of a framed structure is built so that its natural frequencies and vibration modes are captured for later use in updating a finite element model. The prototype uses simple components that have intrinsic variabilities such as aluminum plates, screws, and polymer blocks that are used in the construction. Results regarding the modal update of the finite element model for characteristics such as modes and frequencies are presented together with the test campaign of the experimental results. The results show that it is possible with relatively little computational effort to obtain a numerical model that is more representative of the experimental prototype.

1. INTRODUCTION

Uncertainties are always present in engineering problems to a certain level. It may appear as a lack of confidence in numerical models or even as aleatory in experimental measurements. What is certain is that this may cause discrepancies that should be minimized, when possible, or restrained. Such uncertainties can be categorized into two main classes, (i) the aleatory uncertainty, which reflects the intrinsic (noncontrollable) variability in possible realizations of an event that is stochastic in nature, and (ii) the epistemic uncertainty, which reflects the lack of knowledge (reducible) about a phenomenon that may affect the outcome of events. The ways these uncertainties can be embedded into engineering models will vary depending on the use one wants to make of this information, to just avoid undesirable situations, turning the model predictions more reliable, or to quantify and identify the sources and the level of such uncertainties.

The first approach dates back original works of [3], [4], and [1] where structural parameters were adjusted based on a minimum variance estimator. They use the sensitivities of merit functions for the mean and covariance of numerical and measured parameters to be minimized. In that paper, Gradient-based methods are used to perform the minimization.

Perturbation methods are also very popular and attractive due to low computational costs when dealing with large numerical models like in [5] and [6].

More recently, it has been proposed methods for model updating based on Bayesian inference [7] and [8], where a posteriori estimates of the probability density function of uncertain parameters are identified based on the knowledge of their prior distribution and measured experimental data like in [9], [10] and [11]. A vast literature exists on methods for Model updating based on non-probabilistic approaches like Interval Analysis [12], Fuzzy arithmetic [13], and [14]. They are supported by the fact that much statistical information is not available and therefore, inferences based on unreliable statistical information, certainly lose their credibility.

Most proposals face common problems like the model evaluation computational costs (especially for those based on sampling) that can make the method unfeasible for

complex models. So, a series of papers proposing sequential surrogate models like, Artificial Neural Networks, Radial Basis functions, Kriging, and Support Vector Machines (like in [15], [16], [17]) emerged as an alternative to using complex and alleviating the costly models. But these gains come at the expense of losing model accuracy.

This article proposes a brief review of the different existing methods for updating the finite element model and applying the sensitivity method, applied in an experimental structure to quantify the uncertainties and adjust the numerical model.

2. FINITE ELEMENT MODEL UPDATING

In detail, a finite element model may not precisely predict the measured results due to simplifications and assumptions made by the users. In general, there are three model errors that might cause inaccurate results: (i) model structure errors, i.e., referred to the uncertainty concerning the governing physical equations, (ii) model parameter errors, addressed to the use of inappropriate boundary conditions and inaccurate assumptions in material properties or to simplify the model and (iii) model order errors, referred to the insufficient discretization of complex systems [18]. For example, in the literature, it is very common that finite element updating is used to adjust variables related to model parameter errors, for example, some difficulties in modeling joints or other complex systems could be compensated for by adjusting the material properties in the relevant elements [19].

In other words, according to [20], the experimental model (M_{exp}), which could be represented by the output response (z_{exp}) (displacement, strains, natural frequencies, mode shapes...), depending on the vector of model uncertainty (ε) and vector of measurement uncertainty (μ). So, the experimental model M_{exp} is represented by the sum of these vectors.

$$M_{exp} = z_{exp} + \varepsilon + \mu \quad (1)$$

Thus, finally, the basic principle of finite element model updating is to reduce and quantify the uncertainties associated with the numerical model to predict accurately the experimental responses represented. So, the model updated (M_{opt}) is given by the difference between the measured data from the experimental model (M_{exp}) and the numerical model response (z_{num}).

$$M_{opt} = z_{num} - M_{exp} \quad (2)$$

The importance of updating and adapting numerical models is diverse. It is possible to note that even a high-fidelity FE model may not predict the measured results. The numerical model is taken into account using bar, rigid body, and mass elements to build all the dynamic responses accurately, but even their nominal model with 2,500,000 DOFs overestimates the acceleration and, consequently, underestimates the fatigue life [21]. So, the authors reduced the uncertainties from elastic modulus, density from parts, and modal damping to predict real measured data from fatigue life.

Recently, [20] have written a review describing the different methods and approaches to update the finite element model. According to their review, the static and dynamic responses could be used to adjust the numerical model. These different responses could be noted in [22] when the authors used static displacement to update a numerical model of a bridge, for example. [23] used just the natural frequencies to update a DLR AIRMOD structure. On other hand, [24] used the multi-response combining the static and dynamic response to predict the measured responses (displacement, strain, mode shapes, natural frequencies) from a structure.

2.1 Finite element model updating methods

Marwala [19] affirms there are two classifications for finite element model updating: direct methods and iterative methods. The first one uses the modal properties to update the numerical model to reproduce the modal measured exactly. The same author points out direct methods do not consider the physical parameters and are computationally efficient to implement. In other words, the stiffness and mass matrix are updated, but they cannot have the physical meaning and, therefore, they cannot be related to physical changes to the finite element in the original model [1], i.e., direct methods tend to give models that represent the measured parameters without any regard to the structure that is being analyzed [19]. In addition, they address another significant disadvantage of reproducing the measured data exactly: the numerical response will be equal to the experimental data with measurement noises.

Friswell and Mottershead list, in [1], some direct methods: Lagrange Multiplier Methods, Matrix Mixing, and Methods from Control Theory. It is possible to obtain detailed explanations about these methods in [1] and [18]. However, the use of these direct methods has decreased according to studies presented in [20].

On the other hand, the iterative methods are the most commonly used in finite element model updating which replaced the direct methods and could be divided into deterministic and stochastic. According to [20] deterministic problems transform the finite element model updating into an optimization problem while stochastic methods address it as a statistical problem focusing on the quantification of uncertainty. The same authors list some iterative methods in their review: The sensitivity-Based Method, Bayesian approach, Markov Chain Monte Carlo approach, computational optimization algorithms (Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Simulated Annealing, etc.), Surrogate modeling (Response Surface-based Method, Artificial Neural Networks, etc.). These methods could improve the correlation between measured data and analytical model by the use of a penalty, i.e., according to [1] a wide choice of parameters to be updated attributing a weighting.

The choice of method will influence the computational efficiency as well as a more accurate description of the actual behavior of the structure, consequently, the results of the model update. For example, in [25], the authors compared the PSO and GA in the Nam O Railway Bridge model. They could note the discrepancies between experimental and numerical results were better in PSO besides reducing the computational time if compared to the GA. Even though, [20] point out the PSO has no guarantee that it will converge to the global optimal value. The same review shows that Simulated Annealing, for example, has low convergence speed and because of that it is not commonly used by users to solve a finite element model updating problem.

Other methods propose to replace the finite element model with analytical or statistical approximations to obtain greater computational efficiency, as the Surrogate model is known. There are many Surrogate models, for example: in [15], it is possible to see a surrogate model based on the kriging model, i.e., a way of modeling a function as a realization of the Gaussian process. An interesting advantage of the surrogate model is

computational time if compare to the finite element model and the feasible to run large-scale models, once the high-fidelity models could present the necessity to use high-performance computing (HPC) due to large computational cost. According to the same authors the surrogate model takes about $1.4e-3s$ and the FE model takes about $10.543s$ to execute their case study, therefore it demonstrates the computational efficiency of this method.

Another classic Surrogate model is the Response-Surface based method. Just like all Surrogate models, the Response-Surface based method proposes to replace the FE model but uses a combination of mathematical and statistical approaches that is valid in the global search space. This method can be seen applied in [22] where the authors choose a first-order polynomial function with 12 coefficients considering only the main static effects of the experimental bridge was employed to construct the Response-Surface based models. The same is implemented in [17] where they construct a Response-Surface model to update the natural frequencies of the Tsing Ma Bridge tower using a quadratic polynomial form.

Marwala [26] compared the Response-Surface based model with the methods based on Genetic Algorithms and Simulated Annealing. He could observe that the surrogate model is more efficient than these other methods.

However, according to the review in [20], it is interesting to note that the main disadvantage is that this method requires the construction of a surrogate model which could be a complex process.

2.2 Sensitivity method

The previous subsection aimed to review the main methods used in finite element model updating and to show their main advantages and disadvantages. However, this subsection. From that, this subsection presents the sensitivity method in detail and the main advantages and disadvantages that justify the choice of this method for use in the case study presented in this article.

Mottershead et al.[27] and Ereiz et al.[20] comment that the sensitivity method is based on linearization of the generally non-linear relationship between measurable outputs

and the model parameters that need correction which is developed from a Taylor series expansion truncated after the linear term.

$$\delta \mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{z}_{exp} - \mathbf{z}_{num}(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \quad (3)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{Z}$ is the vector of errors between the vector experimental response (\mathbf{z}_{exp}) and the vector of numerical response (\mathbf{z}_{num}), and $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_n\}^T$ is the vector of free parameters that can be updated in the numerical model. This equation should be applied to all the samples of the measured output parameters (ns).

So, Equation (4) could be approximated according to Mottershead [27] after truncating the Taylor expansion about the true value of the vector of unknown parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta} = \boldsymbol{\theta}_0 + \frac{\partial \mathbf{z}}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}} \approx \boldsymbol{\theta}_0 + \mathbf{S} \delta \boldsymbol{\theta}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{S} is the sensitivity matrix and $\delta \boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a small variation in $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The residual vector ($\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$) has the same definition as the error between the numerical and experimental response, i.e., the residual vector is given by Equation (5).

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} = \delta \mathbf{Z} - \mathbf{S} \delta \boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (5)$$

So, it could be rewritten by Equation (6).

$$\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \approx \mathbf{z}_{exp} - \mathbf{z}_{num}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathbf{S}(\Delta \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (6)$$

Finally, the sensitivity matrix, for iteration i is given by:

$$\mathbf{S} = \left[\frac{\partial z_j}{\partial \theta_k} \right]_{\theta=\theta_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial z_1}{\partial \theta_k} \\ \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial \theta_1} & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial \theta_2} & \dots & \frac{\partial z_2}{\partial \theta_k} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial z_j}{\partial \theta_k} & \frac{\partial z_j}{\partial \theta_k} & \dots & \frac{\partial z_j}{\partial \theta_k} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where j denotes the number of measured data and k is the number of unknown parameters.

For instance, in [27], the author presents the sensitivity matrix for the undamped eigenvalue response (λ_j) by Equation (8).

$$\mathbf{S} = \left[\frac{\partial \lambda_j}{\partial \theta_k} \right]_{\theta=\theta_i} = \boldsymbol{\varphi}_j^T \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \theta_k} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \theta_k} \right] \boldsymbol{\varphi}_j, \quad (8)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_j$ is the j th mode shape vector, \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix obtained by the FE model and \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix obtained by the FE model.

At each iteration, Equation (9) is solved for $\Delta\theta_i$ as:

$$\Delta\theta_i = \theta - \theta_i, \quad (9)$$

and the model is then updated by:

$$\theta_{i+1} = \theta_i + \Delta\theta_i, \quad (10)$$

So, the sensitivity method can be solved by any gradient-based method like in this paper by a Newton-Rahpson-based scheme [2].

Mottershead [27] defines for overdetermined case, where the number of measurements is larger than the number of parameters, the $\Delta\theta_i$ is given by:

$$\Delta\theta_i = [\mathbf{S}_i^T \mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z} \mathbf{S}_i]^{-1} \mathbf{S}_i^T \mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z} \mathbf{r}_i \quad (11)$$

where the $\mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z}$ represents the weighting matrix which accounts for the importance of each individual term in the residual vector.

From that, to adjust the parameters of a given initial analytical model in such a way that the behavior of the model corresponds as closely as possible to the measured behavior, it is necessary to minimize the error between numerical and experimental response (ε_z). This is presented by the objective function in Equation (12).

$$\text{minimise } J(\theta) = J_\varepsilon(\theta) + \lambda^2 J_\theta(\theta), \quad (12)$$

being λ the regularisation parameter, $J_\varepsilon(\theta)$ and $J_\theta(\theta)$, functions that account for the residuals of measured values and the parameter changes, respectively, given by:

$$J_\varepsilon(\theta) = \varepsilon_z^T \mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z} \varepsilon_z \quad (13)$$

$$J_\theta(\theta) = \Delta\theta^T \mathbf{W}_\theta \Delta\theta \quad (14)$$

Therefore, the objective function could be rewritten by Equation (15).

$$\text{minimise } J(\theta) = \varepsilon_z^T \mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z} \varepsilon_z + \lambda^2 \Delta\theta_i^T \mathbf{W}_\theta \Delta\theta_i \quad (15)$$

Finally, the \mathbf{W}_θ is the weighting matrix given by Equation (16) that constrains the parameters according to their sensitivity. Consequently, this ensures that parameters remain unchanged if their sensitivity approaches zero.

$$\mathbf{W}_\theta = \frac{\text{mean}(\text{diag}(\Gamma))}{\text{mean}(\text{diag}(\Gamma^{-1}))} \quad (16)$$

being Γ given by:

$$\Gamma = \text{diag}[\mathbf{S}_i^T \mathbf{W}_{\varepsilon_z} \mathbf{S}_i] \quad (17)$$

Mottershead [27] still comments that if the regularisation parameter (λ) is too small then the problem will be too close to the original ill-posed problem, but if λ is too large then the problem solved will have little connection with the original problem.

2.3 Large scale applications

It is possible to find several practical large-scale applications for finite element model updating (FEMU) in the literature. This shows that machine learning concepts for structural analysis and uncertainty quantification are widely used and a very robust subject.

For example, in the automotive industry, the dynamic responses are compared to support design optimization in the field of NVH engineering [28]. The end-users from BMW, Rover, and Renault companies could validate the methodology by adjusting the mass and stiffness matrix in their automotive framework large-scale FE models. In [29], an automotive transmission is used to minimize the differences between test and numeric analysis. The FE model with 16,800 elements was adjusted by updating the stiffness, mass properties, and modal damping. Recently, a FE model of the rear subframe was built containing 475,544 degrees of freedom (DOFs) to quantify the parameter uncertainty [30]. The authors divided the FE model into different groups to identify the structure parameters.

In addition to it, in the aerospace and aeronautic industry, approximately 360,000 DOFs and 74,000 elements compose a Gravity Field and Steady-State Ocean Circulation Explorer (GOCE) satellite model. Again, the authors created 18 groups to reduce the number of parameters and to make feasible the model updating process using dynamic responses [31]. In [27] a whole model of a baseline Lynx helicopter was updated using the elastic modulus for 147 groups of elements.

3. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL MODEL

The frame structure used in the experiments is composed of three aluminum bars, two PLA supports connecting the three bars and two steel supports attached to two aluminum bars, and are used to fix the model. Figure 1 shows a sketch from the bi-dimensional model of the structure with main dimensions, respective materials, and the experimental model.

Following some procedures presented in the large-scale applications subsection, the numerical model was divided into 19 element groups, presented in Figure 2. The same Figure shows the element size and the number of elements used to build a plane stress FE model (144 elements and 406 DOFs). It uses a linear quadrilateral element with reduced integration (1x1 Gauss quadrature) for the lumped mass matrix and a modal damping matrix to obtain the natural frequencies of the FE model.

Figure 1 – Model detailing and respective materials (a). Experimental model (b).

Figure 2 – FE model and element groups for finite element model updating.

These element groups represent the parameter numbers that are used in finite element model updating, i.e., each element group represents an elastic modulus parameter that must be adjusted by the Sensitivity Method. In addition, the specific mass from each material (3 parameters) and the modal damping of the first four mode shapes (4 parameters) are also adjusted. Table 1 presents all 28 parameters used in finite element model updating and their initial, lower and upper values. From E_1 to E_9 represent the aluminum elastic modulus, from E_{10} to E_{15} for PLA and from E_{16} to E_{19} for steel material. ρ_i , $i = 1,2,3$ represents the specific mass for each material aluminum, PLA, and steel, ζ_i , $i = 1,2,3,4$ represents the generalized equivalent viscous damping ratio for each of the updated modes frequency.

The configuration of the groups described in Figure 2 was previously tested with the intention of separating the group of elements where the screws are located, since, due to the tightening of the screws, there may be a significant difference in the stiffness of these elements. These element groups, where the screws are located, were described by $E_1, E_3, E_4, E_6, E_7, E_9, E_{10}, E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{15}, E_{18}, E_{19}$.

Table 1 - Initial, lower and upper values of all 28 parameters*.

Parameters	Lower Value	Initial Value	Upper Value
E_2, E_5, E_8	$55 \times 10^9 Pa$	$69 \times 10^9 Pa$	$82.80 \times 10^9 Pa$
$E_1, E_3, E_4, E_6, E_7, E_9$	$3.45 \times 10^9 Pa$	$69 \times 10^9 Pa$	$82.80 \times 10^9 Pa$
E_{11}, E_{14}	$2.40 \times 10^9 Pa$	$3 \times 10^9 Pa$	$3.60 \times 10^9 Pa$
$E_{10}, E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{15}$	$1.50 \times 10^8 Pa$	$3 \times 10^9 Pa$	$3.60 \times 10^9 Pa$
$E_{16}, E_{17}, E_{20}, E_{21}$	$168 \times 10^9 Pa$	$210 \times 10^9 Pa$	$252 \times 10^9 Pa$
E_{18}, E_{19}	$10.50 \times 10^9 Pa$	$210 \times 10^9 Pa$	$252 \times 10^9 Pa$
ρ_1	$2160 kg/m^3$	$2700 kg/m^3$	$3240 kg/m^3$
ρ_2	$1000 kg/m^3$	$1250 kg/m^3$	$1500 kg/m^3$
ρ_3	$6240 kg/m^3$	$7800 kg/m^3$	$9360 kg/m^3$
ζ_1	0.00126	0.0126	0,01512
ζ_2	0.00057	0.0057	0,00684
ζ_3	0.00090	0.0090	0,01080
ζ_4	0.00117	0.0117	0,01404

*The vector of uncertain parameter θ will multiply each of the initial values of the uncertain variables, i.e. E_i is represented by θ_i .

The objective function (F) used in this paper to be optimized and obtain the model parameters was chosen to be defined as:

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^{nmode} (z_i^{exp} - z_i^{num}) / z_i^{exp}, \quad (19)$$

where $nmode$ is the number of mode frequencies used in the model updating, exp means the obtained experimental values, num stands for the numerical values, and z_i means the dynamic responses (four mode frequencies and four modal damping ratio) for the finite element model are being updated. For example, $z_i^{num} = z(\theta_j)$ is a function of the parameters θ_j elected to the updated, defined in Table 1, and is obtained by a complete FEM analysis.

3.1 Experimental setup

The base of the frame structure was fixed on a rigid table and it was excited by an impact modal hammer. The impact location is presented in Figure 3. To avoid the rebound effect and to excite only lower modal frequencies, a rubber tip was used with the impact hammer. Accelerometers were attached to each of the aluminum members to measure the vibrations signals from the impact in such a way they were not located on nodal modes. The ADXL 203 accelerometers by Analog Devices were used. They have a 970 mV/g sensitivity and a maximum acceleration measurement of ± 1.7 g, with a frequency range from 0 to 550 Hz. The acceleration signals were acquired with a Measurement Computing 12-bit USB acquisition board at a sampling rate of 1000 Hz. The same Figure 3 presents the precise accelerometer's location. The modal hammer is the Endevco Isotron 4416, with a sensitivity of 1.14 mV/N connected to a signal conditioner Endevco Isotron 4416-1 with 10X gain. 50 measurement data were generated to obtain averages, standard deviations, and covariance to use in the finite element model updating process.

All the experimental data are available in [32] where the reader can download and run the paper's data to reproduce the experimental test and numerical results.

Figure 3 – Measurement detailing for modal analysis, hammer excitation, and accelerometer location.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the experimental and numerical results obtained during the steps of the finite element model updating.

4.1 Experimental results

An example of experimental data used to obtain the natural frequencies and modal damping ratios is shown in Figure 4. This curve represents the 10th measurement. In this same Figure, it is possible to notice the graph containing the acceleration in the time domain from the third accelerometer described in Figure 3. Based on the acceleration time history, the spectrum graph in the frequency domain is obtained using Fourier Transform. It uses the peak-picking method to identify the natural frequencies and gather each mode frequency from raw data, as shown in **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.** using the red circles. After capturing the natural frequencies of each curve, the mean, standard deviation, and covariance for all 50 measurements were evaluated. These results are shown in **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.** To capture the four modal damping ratios (ζ_i) it was used the logarithmic decrement method to graph acceleration histories as presented in Figure 6 using the red line.

Table 2 - Average, standard deviations, and covariance from experimental data.

	Natural Frequencies (Hz)				Modal Damping			
	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	ζ_1	ζ_2	ζ_3	ζ_4
\bar{X}	36.43	154.16	246.22	294.23	0.0126	0.0057	0.0090	0.0117
σ	0.1184	0.4205	0.9475	0.6661	0.0052	0.0008	0.0015	0.0017
COV	0.0032	0.0027	0.0038	0.0023	0.4156	0.1448	0.1682	0.1476

Figure 4 - Experimental data obtained by the third accelerometer.

Figure 5 - Spectrum graph in the frequency domain.

Figure 6 – Logarithmic decrement method to graph acceleration histories.

In

Figure 7, a histogram was plotted referring to the fourth natural frequency in (a) and the fourth modal damping ratio in (b). It is possible to observe that the experimental data chosen to plot follows a normal distribution trend.

Figure 7 – Histogram from 4th natural frequency (a) and 4th modal damping ratio in (b).

One way to demonstrate the scattering of measured data is to plot them on a confidence ellipse. In this ellipse, a point cloud is generated with each of the measured data. Each ellipse is a level set of the multidimensional probability density function. The area of the ellipse represents the probability that a given measured point is within a defined

interval value. For example, in Figure 8 the confidence ellipse is shown comparing the data of the third and fourth natural frequencies. In the same Figure, it can be seen that there are three ellipses, the minor ellipse represents the confidence interval of 68.2% of the dataset (1σ), the intermediate ellipse represents the confidence interval of 95.4% of the dataset (2σ) and, finally, the major ellipse represents the confidence interval of 99.7% of the dataset (3σ).

Figure 8 - Confidence ellipse for the experimental dataset: 3rd and 4th natural frequency.

Therefore, from the confidence ellipse plot, it is possible to observe that only 3 points are outside the 2σ confidence interval, which demonstrates a small dispersion of the measured data. On the other hand, for example, the variation in the data f_3 and f_4 on their respective axes (x and y) represent an elongation and a flattening of the ellipse. Finally, the slope of the main axis of the ellipse is directly linked to the coefficient of correlation between the output parameters f_3 and f_4 . The covariance results and the respective correlation coefficients will be discussed and presented later along with the numerical results.

As explained, one of the objectives is to make the numerical results able to predict the mean, standard deviation, and confidence ellipses of the experimental data. In this way, the finite element model will be able to predict not only the average result but the statistical

data and correlation of the experimental prototype. This will be presented in the next section with the output results of the four natural frequencies and the four modal dampings ratio.

4.2 Numerical results

The results of the initial finite element model, i.e., unadjusted, are shown in **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.** In this table, it is possible to observe that there is a maximum percentage error of 37.34% for the 4th natural frequency and it is notice a percentage error of 00.00 % for all modal damping ratio because of the use of modal damping on the finite element. **Erro! Fonte de referência não encontrada.** presents the four modal shapes of the structure for the initial numerical model (unadjusted model).

Table 3 - Initial numerical model results.

	Natural Frequencies (Hz)				Modal Damping			
	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	ξ_1	ξ_2	ξ_3	ξ_4
\bar{X}	48.54	172.37	322.84	404.08	0.0126	0.0057	0.0090	0.0117
Error (%)	33.23	11.81	37.34	37.34	00.00	00.00	00.00	00.00

Figure 9 – Mode shapes for the initial numerical model (unadjusted).

The previous results represent the initial mode shapes of the finite element model. Therefore, it is clear that there are discrepancies between the experimental and numerical models that will be minimized using Equation (19). Figure 10 presents the convergence process and it is possible to notice the performance of the algorithm until the 40th iteration where the value of the objective function fluctuates over the value of 1×10^{-9} . After the 100th iteration, the value of the objective function reaches the value of 2.8623×10^{-9} . This

shows the main advantage of using the sensitivity method since the procedure converged very quickly with few iterations and thus few objective function calls.

Figure 10 - Convergence history for Mean Square Error (MSE) of the objective function.

After convergence, Table 4 presents the uncertainty quantification (unknown parameter) of all 28 parameters after the finite element model updating process. In the Table 4 is noticed that $\theta_1, \theta_4, \theta_6, \theta_9, \theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{18}, \theta_{19}$ has a low value of mean unknown parameters due to tightening of screws and assembly conditions.

Table 4 - Uncertainty quantifications for all 28 unknown parameters.

Parameters	Mean unknown parameteres	Standard deviation
θ_1	0.0841	0.0055
θ_2	1.2000	0.0226
θ_3	1.1741	0.0046
θ_4	0.0871	0.0052
θ_5	1.0515	0.0328
θ_6	0.0878	0.0053
θ_7	1.1740	0.0046
θ_8	1.2000	0.0225
θ_9	0.0835	0.0057
θ_{10}	1.1777	0.0034
θ_{11}	0.9983	0.0024
θ_{12}	0.5574	0.0085
θ_{13}	0.5577	0.0084
θ_{14}	0.9984	0.0024

θ_{15}	1.1777	0.0034
θ_{16}	0.9960	0.0001
θ_{17}	0.9648	0.0004
θ_{18}	0.6180	0.0055
θ_{19}	0.6174	0.0056
θ_{20}	0.9654	0.0004
θ_{21}	0.9959	0.0001
θ_{22}	1.1488	0.0093
θ_{23}	1.1280	0.0133
θ_{24}	1.0328	0.0013
θ_{25}	1.0000	0.4157
θ_{26}	1.0000	0.1448
θ_{27}	1.0000	0.1682
θ_{28}	1.0000	0.1476

The measured statistical data of damped frequencies and modal damping is presented in Table 5, for a set of 50 samples, which were obtained independently. In this Table, it is observed that the adjusted model was able to reduce the existing discrepancy between the experimental data and the numerical model. The mean value of the four measured natural frequencies were reproduced exactly and their standard deviation have presented a maximum percentual error of 13.34 % to the 3rd natural frequency. The same behaviour is noticed in the mean value of modal damping ratio when the maximum percentual error was 0.00 %. The maximum percentual error of 6.67 % was noticed in the standard deviation of the 3rd modal damping ratio.

Table 5 - Adjusted numerical model results.

Parameter	Experimental		Identified		Percentual Error	
	\bar{X}	σ	\bar{X}	σ	$E_{\bar{X}}$ (%)	E_{σ} (%)
f_1	36.43 Hz	0.1184	36.43 Hz	0.1085	0.00	8.36
f_2	154.16 Hz	0.4205	154.16 Hz	0.4699	0.00	11.75
f_3	246.22 Hz	0.9475	246.22 Hz	0.8211	0.00	13.34
f_4	294.23 Hz	0.6661	294.23 Hz	0.6464	0.00	2.96
ξ_1	0.0126	0.0052	0.0126	0.0053	0.00	1.92
ξ_2	0.0057	0.0008	0.0057	0.0008	0.00	0.00

ξ_3	0.0090	0.0015	0.0090	0.0014	0.00	6.67
ξ_4	0.0117	0.0017	0.0117	0.0018	0.00	5.88

Figure 11 represents the experimental and adjusted confidence ellipses of damped modal frequencies using the sensitivity method. All four damped modal frequencies ellipses were adjusted with very good agreement, which means they are almost identical to the experimental ones. In the same Figure, ellipses showed a standard deviation predicted exactly, but the slope of the ellipses is not exactly the same, but it has a very good agreement.

Figure 11 - Experimental and adjusted confidence ellipses for the first 4 modal frequencies.

Figure 12 represents the experimental and adjusted confidence ellipses of modal damping using the sensitivity method. According to Table 5, the modal damping predicted

exactly the modal damping ratios and their standard deviation this is explain why the ellipses are the same for the experimental and numerical model.

Figure 12 - Experimental and adjusted confidence ellipses for the first 4 modal damping ratios.

The correlation coefficients matrix is a normalized measurement from covariance that presents the correlation between two datasets, i.e., if two variables have a positive and strong correlation value (0.8 to 1.0) thus for a positive increase in the first variable, there is also a positive increase in the second variable. However, for a negative correlation (-1.0), a positive increase in the first variable, there is a negative increase in the second variable. Obviously, a correlation value of 0.0 or a weak correlation value (0.0 ~ 0.2) means that these two variables don't have a linear correlation.

Therefore, the correlation coefficients matrix is an important result in the sensitivity method due to the proposal to update the statistical data of the prototype. In **Figure 13**, it is possible to compare the correlation coefficient between the experimental output vector

and the numerical output vector. In the same **Figure 13** is noticed that the numerical model could predict the correlation between the four damped frequencies (represented by the 1st to 4th row and 1st to 4th column). If the 1st damped frequency is compared to the 2nd damped frequency after updating process, it is noticed a correlation coefficient value of 0.21 is noted, with an absolute error of 0.01 concerning the experimental correlation coefficient value of 0.21, for example. On the other hand, the experimental correlation coefficient of the $f_1 \times f_3$ is +0.42 while the numerical correlation coefficient presented by Figure 13 is +0.42. This explains why the slope of the damped frequency ellipse is slightly different.

In the same way, the correlation coefficient matrix presents that the numerical model predicted so well the experimental value of the modal damping ratio. These values are presented by the 5th to 8th row and 5th to 8th column in **Figure 13**. For example, if the 1st modal damping ratio is compared to the 2nd modal damping ratio, it is noticed an experimental correlation coefficient value of +0.29 when compared to the numerical one of +0.23. This explains why the slope of the ellipses of modal damping ratio is so good.

Figure 13 - Comparison of correlation coefficient matrix for experimental and numerical output vector.

Figure 14 (b) was obtained using the mean unknown parameters presented in Table 4. This figure presents the four natural frequencies and mode shapes of the frame. To ease

the visualization of differences between the initial and final configuration, the results for the initial model (unadjusted) were presented in (a) and the final model (adjusted) in (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 14 - Comparison of modal forms between the initial (a) and final model (b).

Finally,

Figure 15 and Figure 16 present the Receptance (m/N) of the adjusted (represented by a red line) and unadjusted models (represented by a black line) to compare the Frequency Response Function (FRF). The curves below represent the displacement in a specific degree of freedom m when it experiences a force in a degree of freedom n which it is written H_{mn} . It was plotted two receptance curves $H_{163,33}$ in the Figure 15 and $H_{247,33}$ in the Figure 16 just for comparison purposes.

In Figure 15 it is possible to observe that there are only 2 FRF peaks in the model not updated and, for the adjusted model, there are 4 FRF peaks. In Figure 16 one can notice that the FRF peaks just shift back in the frequency axis and increases the amplitude. This highlights the importance of updating the finite element model to get more reliable FRFs of the updated structure.

Figure 15 – Receptance $H_{163,33}$ (m/N) from unadjusted and adjusted models.

Figure 16 – Receptance $H_{247,33}$ (m/N) from unadjusted and adjusted models.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The sensitivity method was used to adjust the dynamic responses (natural frequency and modal damping ratio) of a frame structure consisting of three aluminum bars, two PLA supports connecting the three bars and two steel supports fixed to two aluminum bars. For this, the mass, stiffness and modal damping matrix were updated from 28 parameters previously chosen and demonstrated throughout the text.

The experimental natural frequencies obtained, using the peak-picking method, were: 36.43 ± 0.1184 Hz, 154.16 ± 0.4205 Hz, 246.22 ± 0.9475 Hz and 294.23 ± 0.6661 Hz. After the update process, the natural frequencies obtained for the numerical model were: 36.43 ± 0.1085 Hz, 154.16 ± 0.4966 Hz, 246.22 ± 0.8211 Hz and 294.23 ± 0.6464 Hz. Therefore, the mean value for the damped frequencies were updated exactly and the standard deviation for each value was very well adjusted, presenting a maximum percentage value of 13.34% for the third natural frequency. The values for the modal damping ratios had a very similar behavior, the experimental data showed values equal to: 0.0126 ± 0.0052 , 0.0057 ± 0.0008 , 0.0090 ± 0.0015 and 0.0117 ± 0.0017 , the updated model showed values equal to: 0.0126 ± 0.0053 , 0.0057 ± 0.0008 , 0.0090 ± 0.0014 and 0.0117 ± 0.0018 . Therefore, the mean values were accurately adjusted and the updated standard

deviation showed a smaller percentage error (maximum observed value of 6.67%) than those observed for natural frequencies.

The precision calculated for mean values and standard deviations becomes clear when observing the value obtained for the extremely low mean square error of 2.8623×10^{-9} , which demonstrates the convergence of the sensitivity method. In this way, the confidence ellipses also show a good agreement for the natural frequencies and modal damping ratios both in the size of their semi-axes and in the rotation in the plane. This indicates that the correlation between the numerical output data was precisely fitted to the correlation of the experimental output data. Obviously, this was clear when plotted the correlation coefficients for each output vector.

All unknown parameters were adjusted to physically acceptable values, despite low values for unknown parameters, i.e. θ_4 or θ_6 , shown in places where screws are found. This is expected, since it was noticed that the stiffness in the elements close to the PLA material is very different due to the tightening of the screws and assembly conditions.

Finally, the receptance curve ($H_{163,33}$), presented in Figure 15, capture of the 4 expected peaks for the FRF. Since the initial model showed only 2 peaks.

So, since the updated model predicted the statistical results of the experiment (mean value, standard deviation, correlation of dynamic responses) accurately, this suggests that the updated model can be reliably used to predict dynamic behavior and makes it clear that the initial (unadjusted) model has uncertainties that cause discrepancies between the experimental data and the numerical model.

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